

Analysis of the Film *Un Chien Andalou*

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Abstract: This is an analysis of the short film *Un Chien Andalou* (1929), also known as *An Andalousian Dog*, directed by Luis Bunuel which is an experimental one made with the surrealistic approach and co-written by Salvador Dali, the celebrated surrealist painter. The article utilizes semiotic analysis, including psychoanalytical hypothesis of Oedipus Complex to comprehend the silver screen. The article also employs narrative analysis to understand the surrealistic depiction in reference to the cinematic tools.

Plot Segmentation

1. **Title: Credits**
2. **Title Card: Once Upon a Time**
3. **Room: Near the Balcony/ Unknown**
 - a. A middle-aged man sharpens his razor blade.
 - b. A woman is held by a man's hand focusing her eye.
 - c. The cloud goes through the moon.
 - d. The woman's eye is slitting with the razor (In real, an animal's eye).
4. **Title card: Eight Years Later**
5. **Urban Street**
 - a. A young man bicycles wearing a nun's attire and has a striped box with a strap around his neck.
6. **Apartment Upstairs, The Road**
 - a. A woman reading and heard the bicycle coming.

- b. The young man falls on the ground, the woman comes down.
 - c. The woman reserves the memory of the young man.
 - d. The young man looking at his hand, ants in the palm.
 - e. A woman's armpit, grass, footstep.
 - f. Another woman with a stick in the road looking at a severed hand.
 - g. The woman accidents by a car.
 - h. The young man approaches to the woman sexually.
 - i. The man suddenly comes with two donkeys on two pianos bound with another two men.
 - j. The woman tries to get relieved from the man.
 - k. Title Card: Around three in the morning**
 - l. A second young man knocks the door when the first one was lying in the bed.
 - m. Title Card: Sixteen Years Before**
 - n. The first one kills the second one.
 - o. The second young man falls on a ground (no spatial relation).
 - p. The woman comes in the room, the young man appears again.
7. **The Seashore**
- a. The woman comes to another man, was waiting for her, walks with him.
 - b. Title Card: In Spring**
 - c. A freeze frame, the woman and the man are buried half of their body in the sand.
8. **End Credits**

Introduction

“The interpretation of dreams is the *via regia* (royal highway) to a knowledge of the unconscious element in our psychic life” (Freud, *The Interpretation of Dreams*, 1899, p. 318).

Sigmund Freud, the founding father of psychoanalysis, had a deep insight over suppressed human desires and their relations to and inner force behind the overall human works and relationship.

Un Chien Andalou is a short film based on the psychoanalytic theory and with surrealist approach directed by Louis Bunuel and planned by Salvador Dali with him from two dreams of both the artists.

Surrealism

Surrealism means „truer reality“^{ci}. It is a twentieth century cultural movement began in the 1920s with a thought that was provoked mostly by Sigmund Freud and led by Andre Breton. Artists of this genre think that dream or subconscious mind of human being is the actual way to know the person, how he is actually or what is the truer reality of the humankind. Every person is somehow different in appearance than one's actual kind. The context around the person shapes him to be like that. What we actually think about a thing, we never express the notion in the same way. There works a censorship while the words or works come out of the thoughts in reality that what we should do or say. And the social, political, economic context shapes the censor. Surrealists want to break the censorship in their works. They want to express the truer reality that means what actually a person is like. That is why Sigmund Freud utters

“The dream is the liberation of the spirit from the pressure of external nature, a detachment of the soul from the fetters of matter” (Freud, 2012, p. 8).

Thus, in this film, the surrealist thoughts have been mastered and we need to realize the things from this viewpoint.

Analysis Method

There are some common things while discussing or analyzing a film. But as *Un Chien Andalou* is made out of conventional system, there needs to have some different approaches to have deeper insight about the film. It is a film that subtly worked with the suppressed desires of human being from different perspective. Every shot of the film bears some kind of inner meaning.

It can be analyzed with the semiotic analysis approach as every element here refers something important. Again, it can be analyzed with the storytelling approach which includes the Oedipus Complex theoryⁱⁱ and with this the basic elements and form of the film will also can be discussed.

Semiotic Analysisⁱⁱⁱ

If we want to do the semiotic analysis we need to concentrate towards some elements and props in the film like: 1. The Razor, The Cloud And The Eye; 2. The Attire Of The Young Man; 3. The Box And The Key Hole; 4. The Tie; 5. The Hand; 6. The Ant; 7. The Armpit; 8. The Donkey; 9. The Book; 10. The Moth And The Butterfly; 11. The Grasshopper And The Dragonfly; 12. Physical Posture Of The Characters.

1. The Razor, The Cloud And The Eye

The idea of the film came from the two dreams of Salvador Dali and Luis Bunuel where Bunuel dreamt about a cloud which sliced the moon and Dali dreamt a razor blade slicing an eye.

In the first sequence, we see the cinematic view of these two dreams. With slicing the eye, it may refer that the audience need to watch the film with a different eye to understand. As here vitreous humor came out of the eye, we need to come out of all the conventional methods of watching things.

2. The Attire Of The Young Man

In the second sequence where the title shows „eight years later“ we see a young man riding a bicycle wearing the dress-up of a nun. The person is male; if he were to be a church personality, he should wear the dress of a priest, but he did the opposite. Here raises the question, why?

As this film tries to make it out the inner desires of human from surrealist perspective, it also does a satire to the traditional religious matters as in Christianity where the inner desires of the priests and nuns are suppressed, where church regulated social system is a barrier to natural human thoughts, feelings, works though the system itself does not maintain the regulations always.

The Priest or nun is bound to suppress all the desires especially sexual desires but human mind, as Freud compared it with an iceberg which floats with one-seventh of its bulk above water, somehow acts differently than could be seen. The inner lust of a young person is depicted subtly through the attire.

3. The Box And The Key Hole

A box is something to keep inside. People keeps their important things in the box. In this film, the box is used to portray as the container of human memory. At first, we see the box hanging from the neck of the young man. A close up of the box is shown where we see the key hole and

after that the next shot shows the young lady reading in a room. Here is a link up with the key hole and the lady as its resemblance with the female organ. Maybe it is indicating that at young age, the way of sexual enjoyment is to open the door of gamic world.

Again, we see later that the young girl takes out the tie of the young man and keeps it on the bed and his memory comes in her mind. Later, we see another young girl who embraces the box where the box contains the cut off hand of the young man. Third time we see another young man taking the box from the young man lying in the bed and throws it out of the window. Last time we see the box in the seashore, broken, all the things split up and the women and the person with him neglects it, kick it and left the box and others with it behind. If we take the box as the container of memory, at very first we will find that the two women was very much sorry about their memory and was pale. But as the box represents not only the memory but also the symbol of sexual desire of human and sometimes the desire fulfillment is done with an unethical way, the second man compels him to through away his lust. At last we see the women and the person with him neglects the box as they neglect the memory of the young man. It is a simple human tendency that they want to go with new falling back the memories though it was important to them once.

4. The Tie

If we look back to the history of tie, we will find that it came through the Christians as a symbol of crucifixion of Jesus. It is a memory holder as the woman in the film keeps the tie of the young man which he found in the box, in the bed and thoughts of him. Again, as it came from the crucifixion, it also refers the film's relation or the satire to the church based social system, satire to the bourgeois.

5. The Hand

We see the use of hand in the film was emphasized in different ways. At first, we see a hand is sharpening the razor blade, slicing the eye. Then, we see the hand of the young man where he is watching that ants are coming out of a hole in his palm. After that, the cut off hand fallen in the road and a woman keeps it with her in the box. Next, we see hands are used to fulfill the sexual desire of the young man. Again, we see the hand is stuck in the door by the women and that causes much pain to the young man.

The repetition of hands in *Un Chien Andalou* is, to put it simply, a symbol of fetish. The repetition of wounded and severed hands in the film represents castration fear, and more specifically, a disembodied phallus. This is emphasized when we realize that all the hands, whether injured or exuding ants, are male.

Hand is something that can give pleasure as well as pain to the human. A hand can be used in good work as well as in bad. So, the hand we perceive can be understood by the binary oppositions as Swiss linguist Ferdinand de Saussure states,

“The human mind makes sense of the world essentially by forming binary oppositions” (Berger, 2011, p. 18).

So, hand is used in the film with a surrealistic approach as we see also in the paintings of Salvador Dali where he examined with his hand in different ways.

6. The Ant

We see ants in the palm of the young man. Ant is symbol of decay. Ant goes where there is rotten things, dead and also ants go for sweets. As hand is used here as a way to fulfill the human lust, we see the ants are in the hand made a hole in the palm. That refers to the decay of both mental and physical state as a result of unethical desire fulfillment.

7. The Armpit

When the young man and the woman was looking at the man's palm where the ants were there, we see a dissolve from the hand to the armpit of a woman that refers to the sexual desire, the libido and the lust for which the hand, now is in this state, decaying, being eaten by the ants. Again, the armpit hair we see at the last stage of the film when those suddenly or magically grow on the face of the young man and the woman becomes strange. It is also nothing but the desire of the human mind of having sexual relation with the opposite sex.

8. The Donkey

When the woman did not give the man to fulfill his lust we suddenly see he is pulling two ropes where there are tied two other young persons with nun's attire in front and behind them two dead donkeys without eye on the two pianos.

Here again comes the satire to church, the suppressed desires and the reflection of the mental condition after being defended by the woman. He comes with the church personalities and the eyeless donkeys that may refer that his satire to church that though church or Christianity suppress the sexual desires but actually does it maintain all these things as they show? The donkey is seen as the holy animal in Christian religion as it is thought that it bore Jesus and Marry on its back. The eyeless donkey may refer to the blind rules of the church, the authority, a satire to the whole system.

9. The Book

A book is symbol of knowledge, but when the knowledge is misled, it may occur disaster. When we see the second young man compels the first one to put off his desires and punishes him, we see he takes the books from a table that is old, with dirt and filth. The first one's books transform into pistols and he shoots the second one. It may refer the knowledge which is misled and done an evil work.

10. The Moth and the Butterfly

After the killing of the second young man, in the next scene, when the woman enters into the room again, she looks at a moth closely and in the last frame of the film which was titled as „In Spring“ we see there are butterflies on the two sides of the shoulder of the woman. Those may be flowers instead of butterflies but seem more like butterflies than flowers in their shape.

We know moth transforms into butterfly. In the film at, first showing the moth and then the butterflies it may refer to the transition of human thoughts, which is also expressed by the upward face of the woman in the frame.

Again, Christian tradition views a butterfly as a symbol of resurrection. It is a significant symbol came from the Easter season. Butterfly represents soul or spirit. Thus, we can interpret the film“s use of butterfly as the hope of the resurrection of human desires and the goodness of Christian philosophy (Handlon, 2018).

11. The Grasshopper and the Dragonfly

At the last frame, we see the man and the woman half buried in the soil or the sand and the posture is statue like, lifeless. The man is looking down to earth and there is a grasshopper at his left and a dragonfly on his shoulder.

In Christianity, the Dragonfly Totem represents change. As its wings are sensitive to winds, it indicates us to heed about, where proverbial wind blows or where things comes in different ways. As dragonflies are the creatures of the water, and creatures living beside or around water carry symbolism of unconsciousness, dreaming mind as in animal world, water is a symbol of subconscious mind. There also comes surrealist thoughts to find out the inner vision of human mind and the dragonfly in the frame refers to the surrealist approach of the film. The dragonfly is a reminder that when our deeper thoughts rise to the surface we must pay attention. In short, our thoughts, even the deeper ones that we might not be as in-touch with as we are with our conscious thoughts, are responsible for what we see in our lives - in our physical surroundings. Dragonfly lives a short life, and it knows it must live to the fullest with what it has which gives the lesson of being contented with what we have and the lesson of being happy with using those (Debrinconcita, 2018).

Again, the grasshopper symbolizes good luck all over the world.^{iv} When grasshoppers appear in dreams, these have been interpreted as symbols of freedom, independence, spiritual enlightenment, inability to settle down or commit to decision. Grasshopper has ability to connect and understand sound vibrations and this represents the inner voice of human.

So, both the dragonfly and the grasshopper in the same context may represent the human's inner, deep, subconscious thoughts which are not coming out consciously, should be paid attention.

12. Physical Posture of the Characters

In the film, there also needs to look at the physical posture of the characters in different sequence. The posture of the young man was somehow always as he has some problem in walking whereas the woman is faster in her approach. The suppressed desires often make people physically obsolete which is represented by the young man whereas women are faster in their relationship approach about what to do or what not which is represented by the lady here.

Physical posture is mostly to be viewed in the last frame where the two bodies are more than half buried in the sand or soil. The woman is looking upward and the man looking down to the earth. The woman here wants to get relived. She searches for new way of living after all the problems she faced which is symbolized by the butterfly on her shoulder as a symbol of resurrection which is discussed under the heading „The Moth and The Butterfly“.

The man here looking down to the earth may be as a wish to have apology after all his lusts, desires. His subconscious thoughts as in dreams are symbolized by the dragonfly and his apology may get him a good luck in the next time is symbolized by the grasshopper as we discussed about it under „The Grasshopper and the Dragonfly“ heading.

Oedipus Complex

“Oedipus complex, in psychoanalytic theory, a desire for sexual involvement with the parent of the opposite sex and a concomitant sense of rivalry with the parent of the same sex; a crucial stage in the normal developmental process. Sigmund Freud introduced the concept in his *The Interpretation of Dreams* (1899). The term derives from the Theban hero Oedipus of Greek legend, who unknowingly slew his father and married his mother; its female analogue, the Electra complex, is named for another mythological figure, who helped slay her mother” (Encycloaedia Britannica, n.d., para. 1).

Un Chien Andalou can also be analyzed with the Oedipus complex theory where the young woman is mother, the first young man is the son and the second young man acted by the same actor is as father.

Narrative Analysis

Story

As we see in the plot segmentation of the film, we find some incidents happening in the film out of temporal and spatial relationship. We find here some relations with the Oedipus complex theory which we will discuss now.

We see a man sharpening his razor is as the father of the protagonist who is Oedipus here. He is seen slicing the mother’s eye as she has some kind of sexual relationship with their son which will be shown later. After the credit, eight years later, we see the young man(Oedipus) coming with a bicycle to home, Mother hears him coming and becomes anxious. When he falls on the

ground from the cycle, it refers that the innocence of his childhood is lost. When he dies at the road, mother runs to him and adores him. A dissolve then opens to a close shot of the box the boy was carrying. His mother takes it and opens with a key. She mourns for the dead son. Suddenly she sees that the son is back in the room and looking at his hand where there is a hole in his palm and ants are there in the hole. It refers to the evil works of the boy, the sexual desires he fulfilled with his hand as masturbation and sexual relationship with his mother for which the hand is decaying with the ants. The hand is a symbol of phallus here where it is in a threat of castration. The dissolve from the hand to the armpit of a woman relates this which is a metaphor for her pubis.

The hand lying in the road is the protagonist's hand which represents his masturbatory shame, a representation of his burgeoning sexuality. He becomes excited when it is explored by another person who is meant to be androgynous. When she/he takes the stripped box, we seen at first of the film, with the hand in it refers that the boy is giving his new-found sexuality to him/her. When she was killed by the car, the protagonist goes back to his oedipal desire. He approaches to his mother with a sexual lust. The mother at first resists him but at a time, gives in which refers to aggressive submissive nature of sexual relationship of human.

When he caresses her breasts, he visualizes buttocks which signifies the elements of fantasy and displacement in human sexuality, as well as possibly hinting again at homosexual desires within the protagonist because it is impossible to tell whether the buttocks are male or female. He is shown rolling back his eyes in head refers to the blindness which is occurred by the excessive sexual desires fulfilled by masturbation. The consequent problem of this state is also shown by the blood in his mouth. The blindness is also linked with the dead donkeys without eyes. As the

protagonist struggles to reach his mother and satisfy his Oedipal desires, he is burdened by Christian morality, exemplified by the tablets and the priests.

After that a person comes in the home who can be taken as his father who throws out the box which is symbol to his sexual desires and punishes him. The boy's book in his hand becomes two pistols and he kills his father which also represents the Oedipus complex where the boy wants to take the place of his father. The father falls out of the scene in a field touching a nude woman who disappears in a moment refers to the father who lost his wife to his own son.

The mother later is seen looking at a "death's head" moth which refers to her transformation as a result of his son's sexual desire as the moth becomes a butterfly. The comes again and shows his mother the mouth of him indicating „do not tell anyone“, but the mother puts on lipstick as saying „I will tell anyone I like“, but the son reminds her about the sexual relation by growing armpit hair on his mouth. The mother neglects him showing him her tongue and goes out and suddenly comes to a seashore. Her relation with another youth resembles her transformation and her desire of being out of the relationship with her son. We see at last, that the bodies of the mother and the new young person are buried up to their belly and it was a monumental shot or the position of the bodies are monumental because there are butterflies, dragonfly, grasshopper in the freeze frame which refers meaning which is discussed earlier.

Time and Space

There is no temporal and spatial continuity in the film as these are not found in the dreams. As surrealist approach bases on dream and subconscious, it is nicely implemented in the film as in temporal, with the title cards, „Once Upon a Time“, then „Eight Years Earlier“, after that, „Sixteen Years Before“, and at last, „In Spring“

The spatial relationship is broken as we see the father after being shot falls out of the scene in a ground. Again, we see when the mother comes out of the room at last sequence, the outside was totally changed as there was a beach which was a street in the earlier.

Continuity

Out of temporal and spatial matters there are other continuity matters, significant in the film. When we see the young man (main protagonist) comes with a cycle, he is shown with the viewpoint of the woman beside the window. But suddenly the viewpoint was changed as showing from another side of the road.

After falling of the young man from cycle, the cycle wheel is shown rotating and then stopped, after that again rotating, which breaks continuity rule.

Before the car kills the androgynous person in a shot we see that, she drops the box into the ground while the car was approaching; in the next shot, we see no, the box is still in her hand which breaks the continuity shots.

When the father came, we see the boy lying in the bed, but his face from different angles were in a conflict of continuity.

There are some problems in continuity in this film but if we think about the nature of this film that was made based on dream and unconscious, we can say there are no continuity break as in dream, there is never found any kind of continuity.

Lighting

The lighting in the film is more or less the same in everywhere. When to emphasize, things were shown with focusing on the subject.

While showing the night scene, the night mood was well created with light. The shadow of the person with the razor makes the scene more interesting and mysterious, which mystery we see all over the film later.

Little dark in the room made the environment for depicting the surrealist, dreamy visuals.

Another young girl who was standing on the road, her hard shadow may refer the bi sexuality as well as different nature of human being, the outer side and the inner side; the inner side, which is more mysterious and darker to understand.

The monumental posture of the figures, at the last frame of the movie also consists shadows of the two persons which also refers to the two sides of human character, one, we all can see but the other one, is out of our sight, which is full with the suppressed desires.

Music

As silent film, there is no other sound in the film except the music. The music used in the film creates somehow, excitement, relax, desire fulfillment etc.

The first scene we see starts with the exciting music which indicates something unusual is going to be happened. The same music we hear when the protagonist sexually assaults the woman. The film end with the same music.

The disappointment of the father to his son is well described by the music.

The soft and little sorrow music we hear when the protagonist dies, also when he looks at his hand which also refers strangeness. This music ends after a climax is shown with the killing of the second woman by the car.

Editing

The editing of the film works greatly to refer the meaning in the film. It can be called continuity editing till the continuity of the incidents are found. The transition, dissolve is used subtly in different phases.

While the young man was coming by the cycle a superimposed view is shown which reminds the cubism movement where things are seen from different perspectives.

The dissolve from ants in hand to the armpit of a woman refers to the result of uncontrolled sexual things.

Edit works here also depicting things those are not really in the set as we see when the second young man bells the door the first one sees it as a tin pot is knocked by two hands, which only can be possible in dream.

When the second man compels the first man to do things, his movements were shown in slow motion to refer the inner feelings of him. Again, with edit, the books become pistols to refer the bad impact of knowledge while used in wrong way.

The mouth of the young man becomes zipped to refer not to tell anyone and the lipstick and the armpit hair growing on the mouth also refers meanings here described earlier.

All these things are done with the editing to refer to meanings subtly.

A Deep Insight to the Film

Luis Bunuel said in his writings that the main condition of making the film with Salvador Dali was their thoughts

“No idea or image that might lend itself to a rational explanation of any kind would be accepted” (Bunuel, 1986, p. 104). He also stated,

“NOTHING, in the film, SYMBOLIZES ANYTHING. The only method of investigation of the symbols would be, perhaps, psychoanalysis” (Bunuel, 2006, p. 102).

He wanted to shock and insult the intellectual bourgeoisie of that time. As he said,

“Historically the film represents a violent reaction against what at that time called „avantgarde cine“, which was directed exclusively to the artistic sensibility and to the reason of the spectator” (Bunuel, 2006, p. 101).

But he was disappointed when the spectators accepted the film warmly. Dali said, that the reason of making this film was,

“to disrupt the mental anxiety of the spectator,” and one of the easiest ways to do this is to thwart the viewer’s ability to logically interpret proceedings” (Aranda, 1975, p. 64).

The film intended to depict the suppressed inner desires of human beings because they believed that behind of all the things in the world, there works „libido“.

Libido is here with the meaning of lust, with the meaning love, affection and with the meaning of action, the power or energy behind any work.

The church dominated social system as it was denied at the time of renaissance artists, is now also denied by the filmmakers, the surrealists where they are against the capitalists, bourgeois.

Conclusion

Thus, *Un Chien Andalou* has a deep insight to the human nature, mind and activities as well as the social system. As Bunuel says „nothing symbolizes anything“ the film can be explained in many ways according to the perception of the viewers what they really think about these inner thought and social system.

About the Film

Direction : Luis Buñuel
Produced by : Luis Buñuel & Pierre Braunberger
Screenplay : Luis Buñuel & Salvador Dalí
Music : Richard Wagner
Cinematography : Jimmy Berliet
Editing : Luis Buñuel
Language : Silent (French Intertitles)
Release date : 6th June 1929
Country : France

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ⁱ **Surrealism**, movement in visual art and literature, flourishing in Europe between World Wars I and II. Surrealism grew principally out of the earlier Dada movement (Surrealism, 2017).

ⁱⁱ **Oedipus complex**, in psychoanalytic theory, a desire for sexual involvement with the parent of the opposite sex and a concomitant sense of rivalry with the parent of the same sex; a crucial stage in the normal developmental process. Sigmund Freud introduced the concept in his *Interpretation of Dreams* (1899) (ENCYCLOPAEDIA BRITANNICA, n.d., para 1)

ⁱⁱⁱ **Semiotics** is a discipline, in which culture, society and natural phenomena are explored as signs (KOPPA, 2018); science of signs.

^{iv} **Grasshoppers** can just hop forward, not in reverse, or sideways. In this way, when grasshopper shows up he could be reaffirming to you that you are finding a way to push ahead in your present circumstance. Or then again it may be the case that he is instructing you to simply ahead and advance, moving beyond what is obstructing you. This is the reason grasshopper is the image of good fortunes everywhere throughout the world. (Lott, 2018)

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